

A history of dengue fever surveillance in post-Independent India

Final Report for SAGE Senior Ambassadors Program 2025

SAGE Senior Ambassador: Daria Vaccari

Supervisor: Dr. Manisha Sinha

Project: Surveillance

Contributors: Dr. Poonam Trivedi, Dr. Shannon B. Olsson

Abbreviation Key

BI – Breteau Index: Number of positive containers per 100 houses.

CI – Container Index: Percentage of water containers with larvae.

DENV-1 to DENV-4 – Dengue Virus Serotypes 1 to 4: Different strains of dengue virus.

DHF – Dengue Haemorrhagic Fever: Severe form of dengue infection.

HI – House Index: Percentage of houses with Aedes mosquito larvae.

ICMR-NIV – Indian Council of Medical Research – National Institute of Virology: Key lab producing diagnostic kits.

IDSP – Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme: India’s nationwide digital disease surveillance system.

IHIP – Integrated Health Information Platform: Digital platform replacing older IDSP systems.

MSVC – Media Scanning & Verification Cell: Event-based surveillance team that monitors media/social reports for outbreaks.

NCVBDC – National Centre for Vector Borne Diseases Control: Agency under India’s Ministry of Health managing vector-borne disease surveillance.

NIV – National Institute of Virology

NVBDCP – National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme: Older program focused on malaria and later dengue.

PI – Pupal Index: Number of Aedes pupae per 100 houses.

S/P/L – Syndromic / Presumptive / Laboratory-confirmed: Reporting streams used in IDSP.

VRDL – Virus Research & Diagnostic Laboratory: Network of labs for virus testing and serotyping.

WHO – World Health Organization: Global health authority.

Abstract

This report provides a historical analysis of the evolution of the dengue fever surveillance system in India since the country's independence. It considers the development of public health surveillance in India in connection with the country's post-colonial economic and institutional development. The analysis begins with the first virologically confirmed outbreak in 1963 and identifies the 1996 dengue fever epidemic as a critical turning point that led to a paradigm shift in national policy action in regards to dengue fever surveillance. Thereafter, the Report further retraces how the key components of the surveillance system evolved in recent decades. It discusses the development of laboratory networks and systems, specifically looking at the Virus Research and then Diagnostic Laboratories, the multi-tiered Independent Labeling Systems, the NVBDCP, IDSP, and more recently, the IHIP.

However, much more remains to be done. Underreporting has been a recurring issue in India since the first outbreak in Chennai in 1963, as the division of labour across different agencies and territories is still poorly coordinated leading to fragmentation in case reporting. Furthermore, people in rural and periurban areas are especially disadvantaged and vulnerable because of a lack of local health laboratories. The report concludes that while the technological components for a robust system are now in place, their integration remains inefficient and many of the more technical aspects of surveillance are still very underdeveloped and are not prepared for high burden of dengue fever cases India has to reckon with each year, much less for the predicted increase of this burden in the next years. The emerging One Health framework is highlighted as a promising avenue for a more proactive approach. The central argument of this Report is that while India possesses all the necessary elements for effective dengue surveillance, it lacks the channels and tools to ensure strategic cooperation across these disparate data streams to bridge the gap between policy and practical implementation.

Key words: Dengue fever; surveillance; post-independent India; NVBDCP; IDSP; VRDL; IHIP; One Health framework; vector-borne diseases; public health

Introduction

Although dengue fever is widely regarded by the WHO as a major global health threat, its history in India is relatively new. In 1780 in Madras, now Chennai, was the first ever recorded case of dengue fever, and it was only in 1963 that marked the first reported outbreak ([Mutheneni et al., 2017](#)). India has witnessed a 30-fold increase in incidence of dengue fever cases in recent decades ([Pilot et al., 2020](#)), driven by rapid and unplanned urbanization, inadequate water supply and sanitation systems, the climate crisis, and urban population growth, which all create an ideal breeding condition for *Aedes mosquitos*, the vector of dengue fever ([Pilot et al., 2020](#), [Hussain and Dhiman, 2022](#)).

A few pivotal milestones help situate how dengue surveillance emerged and professionalized in post-Independence India. As above-mentioned, clinically “dengue-like” illness was recorded in Madras as early as 1780, but the first virologically confirmed epidemic came much later, in Kolkata and along India’s eastern coast in 1963–1964 ([Gupta et al., 2012](#), [Mutheneni et al., 2017](#)). What really brought national attention (and funding) to the matter was the first major nationwide outbreak of dengue haemorrhagic fever (DHF) in 1996, centred on Delhi and attributed largely to DENV-2, subsequent waves in the 2000s cemented dengue’s near-endemic status across most states, with all four dengue fever serotypes (DENV-1 to DENV-4) circulating with fluctuating incidence by region and year. These historical anchors matter because they track with the gradual evolution from ad-hoc outbreak investigation toward more formal, routine surveillance tied to national programs and laboratory networks ([Gupta et al., 2012](#)).

Given this alarming rise of dengue in India, conducting a historical review of dengue surveillance in India is relevant for understanding how the country’s public health response has evolved in the face of recurring dengue outbreaks so to inform stakeholders and policy makers on the critical turning points, persistent gaps, and best practices in dealing with this

zoonotic disease. Therefore, by tracing the creation and development of dengue surveillance systems, from manual reporting methods to digital platforms like the Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme (IDSP) ([Kant and Krishnan, 2010](#)), all the way to the more novel and integrated approach of One Health, this report seeks to explore how dengue fever surveillance emerged in India and how it was implemented and changed throughout the years. This research will also seek to answer what role national and international agencies played in shaping India's dengue surveillance system, as well as what are the major gaps and limitations in the current system.¹

This report is organised as follows. After a first section outlining the methods used in order to find relevant literature, the report offers a literature review analysing chronologically policy documents and peer-reviewed academic articles by providing a brief economic history of post-colonial India while tracking a history of the country's dengue fever surveillance system, focusing on the above-mentioned research questions. Thereafter, the report will lead to a discussion on how the current surveillance system functions under the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare ([Kumar et al., 2024](#)), and what are its merits, shortcomings and overall limitations. The report concludes by offering some recommendations.

Methods

A search of the literature was conducted to identify relevant empirical studies, reviews and policy documents discussing the history of dengue fever surveillance in India. The databases considered were PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science and JSTOR. The following terms were used for the search: "dengue", "arbovirus", "arboviral infection", "surveillance", "monitoring", "public health", "history", "historical", "temporal trends", "developments", "India", "Indian". The papers were then selected according to their relevance to the research question. Studies were considered regardless of language, publication year, or geographic origin. No exclusion criteria were imposed. The search was further complemented through citation chaining on the selected articles.

¹ This report is part of the echo network's [Surveillance project](#). The echo network is a social innovation platform launched in 2019. It aims to promote collaboration between researchers, policy makers, educators, and local communities to address ecological and environmental challenges in the country. One of the focus areas is how to foster the development of [Clean and Healthy cities](#). In response to the increasing incidence of zoonotic disease cases, the echo network has set out to identify systemic gaps in existing surveillance systems from a One Health perspective, a focus area this report is designed to inform.

Historical Overview

When British rule left India, the economic as well as the geopolitical situation was left in shambles. Under British rule, India's native manufacturing industries shrank. The government of post-independent India had to pick up the pieces of the postcolonial rule and try to reassemble them into a lasting political and economic structure. Pre-independent India had already discussed economic planning prior the independence, and there was a dominant consensus among various political groups that industrialization and import substitutions in order to achieve self-reliance were of the priorities of Indian economic future ([Srinivasan and Tendulkar, 2003](#)). Following the Soviets, who were perceived to have been developing successfully from an agricultural society, the Indian government instituted its first five-year plan ([Srinivasan and Tendulkar, 2003](#)). Britain was indebted greatly to India, as a result of their war expenditure overseas, and this availability of these sterling balances allowed the government to expand in expansionary policies ([Schenk, 2011](#)).

These developmental policies did not succeed as they had hoped for ([Schenk, 2011](#)). In the year between 1947 and 1970s, GDP growth was limited to 3.5% which gave it the name of Hindu growth ([Rodrik and Subramanian, 2004](#)). Meanwhile, China, and other Asian economies which were transitioning from agricultural society to industrialised ones, were growing at a much faster rate managing to relieve its country from poverty. India was lacking behind for an extended period of time, this lengthy stagnation gives plenty of reasons to believe that the economy was not functioning well. Rodrik and Subramanian seem to imply, in their reading of the Indian economic growth process, that this period was of great importance for the institutional basis it provided for the decades to come. In their view, the 1980s, which witnessed a attitudinal change, was significantly allowed to do so by the solid institutional basis that was laid during this period ([Rodrik and Subramanian, 2004](#)). The democracy established in 1950 promoted the investment in high education, as well as clear laws that protected property rights. In this reading, the 1950s–1970s transition period would have had a great impact on institutions that became extremely relevant for the economic growth that manifested itself in the 1990s ([Rodrik and Subramanian, 2004](#)).

Figure 1. GDP per capita in post-independent India. Data from World Bank Group.

At the same time that India was undergoing these institutional transitions in the economic domain, public health surveillance, including for vector-borne diseases like dengue, was also gradually being built up, though on a more fragmented scale. Dengue fever, now a major public health concern, had been recognized clinically in India since the 1960s, but its surveillance infrastructure was underdeveloped until much later ([Mutheneni et al., 2017](#)). This will be further discussed in the second section of this report, but the government at this time relied heavily on existing malaria control systems, and systematic dengue-specific tracking only became prominent during the 1990s in states like Tamil Nadu.

The 1970s experienced a shift in economic priorities and resources allocation. Indira Gandhi was a key figure for Indian economic development in this period. Her Congress aimed at diversifying the economic base and increasing investment ([Panagariya, 2008](#)). In order to do so, priority to the growth of private businesses was given. She reduced controls so that private firms could flourish, and her Congress privatized heavy and large-scale industries and priority sectors in agriculture. The main purpose of the large-scale public sector was to create the necessary infrastructure base that would then allow for the private sector to develop ([Panagariya, 2008](#), [Frankel, 2005](#)).

Although public health infrastructure was not the primary focus of these economic policies, the period did witness the expansion of public hospitals and laboratories, which later became part of dengue surveillance networks. States like Gujarat, Kerala, and Delhi developed early regional surveillance tools, including GIS mapping ([Sarkar et al., 2019](#)) and emergency syndromic alerts, which often performed better than national systems in detecting local dengue outbreaks ([Kant and Krishnan, 2010](#)).

After Indira Gandhi's assassination in 1984, the mantle was passed onto her son Rajiv Gandhi. His government was the first to begin the process of economic liberalisation by fostering new relationships with Western governments and promoted liberalisation of foreign trade and payments, though the opposition from the rural groups, fearing international competition, compelled the state to backtrack on its policies ([Panagariya, 2008](#)).

The economic consequences by the end of the decade was that the economy had advanced in terms of GDP growth, passing from the 3.5% characterised Hindu Growth of the previous years to a more conspicuous 4.8% in the 1980s. Alongside these economic inputs, dengue surveillance funding was considerably increased ([Gupta et al., 2012](#)), which in turn began to benefit from expanded data collection, greater lab confirmation, and increased regional coordination, under new lab networks and funding under the the National Vector Borne Disease Control Programme (NVBDCP), even though it still captured only a fraction of total infections ([Gupta et al., 2012](#)).

Indeed, some estimates suggest that between 2006 and 2012, actual dengue cases may have been nearly 300 times higher ([Shepard et al., 2014](#)) than officially reported figures, due to gaps in the surveillance and reporting infrastructure. While India's institutional economic reforms laid the groundwork for liberalization in the 1990s, public health systems, including dengue surveillance, similarly began to mature with improved frameworks, albeit with persistent challenges of coordination, coverage, and data transparency ([Mutheneni et al., 2017](#), [Gupta et al., 2012](#)).

Dengue Fever Surveillance: Systems and Infrastructure

The historical overview sketched above shows how dengue surveillance emerged slowly, borrowing at first from malaria programs and only gradually developing a

specifically-dedicated outbreak system. The 1960s and 1970s were decades characterised by little understanding and awareness of dengue fever, as well as of sporadic recording of cases ([Gupta et al., 2012](#)). It was in the 1990s that proved a turning point with the 1996 Delhi's haemorrhagic fever epidemic ([Kumar et al., 2024](#)), where the problem of dengue fever could no longer be ignored. The past two decades have been about building a backbone for this relatively new surveillance system, by investing in labs, digital platforms, and policy frameworks to standardise data collection and sharing ([Kant and Krishnan, 2010](#)). This section of the report looks at specific developments that have occurred in regards to dengue fever surveillance in India's post-colonial era.

Laboratory capacity has been at the base of dengue fever surveillance since the 2000s. Since 2007, the NCVBDC began systematic distribution of dengue IgM MAC-ELISA kits produced by National Institute of Virology (NIV) to designated labs nationwide, with NCVBDC covering costs and NIV holding buffer stock for surges ([National Center for Vector Borne Diseases Control, 2023](#)). Over the last decade, the Virus Research & Diagnostic Laboratory (VRDL) network established by the Department of Health Research/ICMR has scaled dramatically to 161 labs as of March 31, 2024 (11 Regional Level, 27 State Level and 123 Medical College Level) ([Department of Health Research, 2025](#)), complementing IDSP and enabling larger volumes of ELISA confirmation as well as RT-PCR for serotyping in many centres ([Indian Council of Research Medicine, 2024](#)). External Quality Assurance rounds coordinated through NIV have standardized kit performance and inter-lab comparability ([ICMR - National Institute of Virology, 2025](#)), which is an important development that makes data trend interpretations more reliable than a decade ago. Although the establishment of 161 is a great step forward, most of those are still based in large urban areas even if the point is to decentralise testing. The bulk of these labs are at a Medical College level, which are intended to serve clusters of districts ([Department of Health Research, 2025](#)), but many are still urban based due to the location of the medical colleges themselves, leaving many rural and non-residential urban areas outside of labs' catchment areas and thus un surveilled until a disease outbreak has already emerged.

Despite these advancements in the Indian surveillance lab network, the issue of systematic underreporting signalled in the 1960s and 1970s was never completely resolved, as independent audits and disease-burden studies showed in recent years. During Delhi's 2015 outbreak, a medical college audit documented that large numbers of dengue patients treated

in private facilities never reached official tallies, which was due to under-reporting both by the public as well as by the private healthcare sector in Delhi ([Thakur, 2016](#)). Nationally, a burden study estimated that true dengue cases could be roughly 280-plus times higher than reported, once care-seeking patterns, test coverage, and non-notified private treatment are accounted for ([Shepard et al., 2014](#)). Taken together, these findings reinforce a long-standing theme of Indian governance in regards to public health surveillance, that keeping track of 1.4 billion people is a task that can only be achieved when data is properly managed and shared.

Efforts have been made in this regard. Originally, it was India's main vector-borne disease program, the NVBDCP, emerged out of malaria programs, which was to track dengue within its purview ([Mutheneni et al., 2017](#)). The program confirmed dengue cases using government-supplied MAC-ELISA² kits, but coverage was uneven and largely passive, relying on sentinel hospitals and outbreak seasons. In 2004, funded in part by the World Bank, the IDSP was launched to provide a more comprehensive system of weekly disease data reporting, one that was created explicitly with the intent of tracking better dengue, and other diseases, cases and outbreaks ([Mutheneni et al., 2017](#)). The IDSP enabled syndromic, presumptive, and lab-confirmed tracking formats, though coordination between NVBDCP and IDSP remains a structural weakness, often leading to underreporting as was the case in Delhi of 2016.

These two systems thus now drive two parallel, and somewhat overlapping, channels of dengue data in India, and they work as follows. The NVBDCP undertakes surveillance for the vector-borne diseases in the country. The programme is set out to focus on the prevention and control of diseases, which include malaria, dengue, chikungunya, Japanese encephalitis, kala-azar as well as lymphatic filariasis ([Mourya et al., 2019](#)). The surveillance of NVBDCP hinges on a large sentinel hospital network and designated labs that confirm cases and report to state and national levels. As of 2025, NVBDCP lists 869 sentinel hospitals and continues to circulate state-wise allocations of dengue IgM kits and related supplies ([National Centre for Vector Borne Diseases Control, 2025](#)). Concurrently, the IDSP is a decentralized, state based surveillance program, that was created to detect early warning signals of impending outbreaks and organise an outbreak response if needed, thereby preventing the outbreak from

² ELISA tests, enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays, are laboratory techniques used to detect and quantify specific substances, such as antibodies, antigens, proteins, and hormones, in biological samples. These tests are widely used in diagnostics, research, and various other fields due to their versatility and high sensitivity ALHAJJ, M., ZUBAIR, M. & FARHANA, A. 2025. Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay. *StatPearls*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing.

spreading further ([Yasobant et al., 2024](#)). It is also expected to provide essential data to monitor progress of on-going disease control programs and help allocate health resources more efficiently ([Kumar et al., 2014](#)). These essential data is compiled weekly counts using three streams, S (syndromic), P (presumptive/clinical), and L (laboratory-confirmed), which are designed to catch signals early (S, P) and then reconcile them with confirmations (L) ([Kant and Krishnan, 2010](#)). In practice, these two systems overlap but don't always communicate smoothly, especially in areas where private-sector care is prevalent, which can inherently result in an exacerbation of data loss and underreporting, one of the very issues the two agencies were set out to resolve.

Digitization has been the biggest structural shift of the 2010s and 2020s in regards to dengue fever surveillance. IDSP's move to the Integrated Health Information Platform (IHIP) beginning in 2018 brought near-real-time, line-listed reporting, GIS mapping, and tighter lab integration to 33 surveillance health conditions including dengue ([Yasobant et al., 2024](#)). Event-based surveillance was also institutionalized via IDSP's Media Scanning & Verification Cell (MSVC), which scrapes and verifies media and social signals for unusual clusters; MSVC alerts routinely trigger rapid response teams to investigate early signals before they become outbreaks ([Integrated Disease Surveillance Programme, 2025](#)). The combination of routine (S/P/L) feeds, lab confirmations, and event-based tips has practically shortened the distance between a signal and an official epidemiological response in many districts.

Entomological surveillance, although less visible than case counts, is integral to how districts decide when to intensify control and ties in with the One Health concept. India's operational guidance tracks "Stegomyia" indices, the House Index (HI), Container Index (CI), Breteau Index (BI), and, increasingly, Pupal Index (PI), to quantify *Aedes mosquitos* breeding ([Kumar and Prasad, 2021](#)). Historically, thresholds like $HI \leq 1\%$ or $BI \leq 5$ were borrowed from yellow fever experience and have been debated for dengue ([Bowman et al., 2014](#)), nevertheless, NCVBDC still operationalizes indices for action thresholds, complemented by zonal entomological teams and insecticide-resistance monitoring. The net effect is that many urban local bodies now pair human surveillance with periodic WHO-recommended larval/pupal surveys and house-to-house source reduction ([Times of India, 2025a](#)), especially ahead of monsoon peaks ([Times of India, 2025b](#)).

On the virological side, surveillance has matured from sporadic isolation to routine serotype tracking. The 1996 Delhi DHF epidemic was dominated by DENV-2, while subsequent years have seen circulation of all four serotypes with geographic and temporal shifts, concurrent infections by multiple serotypes, including reports of all four dengue fever serotypes in Delhi samples, have been documented ([Indian Council of Research Medicine, 2024](#)). Expanded RT-PCR capacity in the VRDL network now makes it feasible for more states to monitor serotype switches in-season, information that can subtly influence clinical triage and preparedness messaging, even though case management remains supportive across serotypes ([Indian Council of Research Medicine, 2024](#)).

A notable policy evolution is India's adoption of a One Health frame that explicitly links human, animal, and environmental data streams. While dengue is human-borne, and therefore technically not a zoonosis disease by the text-book definition of the word, its vector ecology and climate sensitivity make it a natural beneficiary of One Health tooling. Merging rainfall, temperature, water-storage patterns, and urban growth could all be used to keep track of cases and organise disease outbreak resource allocation. Pilot efforts and analyses in 2023–2025 point to this integration as a near-term frontier for smarter dengue early-warning at ward and block level scale ([Indian Council of Research Medicine, 2024](#)). For instance, a study in Gujarat highlighted the development of a robust early warning system through the One Health approach, emphasizing the need for integrated surveillance across sectors ([Yasobant et al., 2025](#)).

The Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) has been instrumental in implementing the One Health Mission ([Office of the Principal Scientific Adviser to the Government of India, 2025](#)), focusing on strengthening surveillance, early warning systems, and research to address both endemic and emerging epidemic threats ([Indian Council of Research Medicine, 2024](#)). In summary, India's One Health initiative is promoting a more integrated and proactive approach to managing dengue fever outbreaks, leveraging cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary data to improve preparedness and response strategies. The effort is laudable, but much has yet to be done to ensure these data are properly handled and shared in a timely manner.

Dengue Surveillance Evolution in India (1963-2024)

Figure 2. Timeline of dengue surveillance evolution in India (1963-2024)

Conclusions and Future Directions

This paper has offered a brief economic history of post-colonial India, and in conjunction to this history it has discussed the development of the currently in use dengue surveillance system in the country. A few shortcomings appear evident from this overview:

1. The IDSP and NCVBDC programs partly share responsibilities, which inherently makes it more difficult to keep one program accountable for dengue fever cases underreporting. The agencies should either be reorganised so that solely one is considered responsible for tracking dengue fever cases, or use the same data system, to ensure that there is no data loss between either party.
2. Another data gap issue that currently exists regards lab QA and the VRDL network. For the vast majority these rounds and tests are solely carried out in large urban centres, leaving rural areas undersurveilled and more vulnerable to consequences of possible disease outbreaks. It is crucial to zoom in at a granular level, focusing on city wards and block levels where dengue fever actually begins spreading, so as to invest resources in a timely and cost-efficient manner.
3. Exploit IHIP and One Health tools to layer vector indices, weather forecasts, and mobility with case data to move from reactive to a proactive outbreak approach. This can be done by promoting the establishment of pre-agreed outbreak action ladders, that can be paired to entomological indices. For example, if HI/BI are found to have crossed seasonal thresholds, then local enforcement can look into container control, and if needed run school-based campaigns and automatically provide hospitals with more resources

To sum up, many parts of the Indian dengue fever surveillance system are already working, albeit often inefficiently. All the pieces to create a comprehensive and proactive surveillance system exist, but the main challenge that persists is to pool these data together to ensure they can be used constructively.

References

- ALHAJJ, M., ZUBAIR, M. & FARHANA, A. 2025. Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay. *StatPearls*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing.
- BOWMAN, L. R., RUNGE-RANZINGER, S. & MCCALL, P. J. 2014. Assessing the relationship between vector indices and dengue transmission: a systematic review of the evidence. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*, 8, e2848.
- DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH RESEARCH. 2025. *Setting up of nationwide network of laboratories for managing epidemics and national calamities* [Online]. Government of India. Available: <https://schemes.dhr.gov.in/vrdlinfo?> [Accessed August 16th, 2025].
- FRANKEL, F. 2005. *India's Political Economy: The Gradual Revolution (1947-2004)*, Oxford University Press.
- GUPTA, N., SRIVASTAVA, S., JAIN, A. & CHATURVEDI, U. C. 2012. Dengue in India. *Indian J Med Res*, 136, 373-90.
- HUSSAIN, S. S. A. & DHIMAN, R. C. 2022. Distribution Expansion of Dengue Vectors and Climate Change in India. *GeoHealth*, 6, e2021GH000477.
- ICMR - NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF VIROLOGY, P. 2025. *Resource Centre for Virus Research and Diagnostic Laboratories (RC-VRDL)* [Online]. Indian Council of Medical Research. Available: <https://niv.icmr.org.in/form/root/resource-centres/resource-centre-for-virus-research-and-diagnostic-laboratories-rc-vrdl> [Accessed August 16th, 2025].
- INDIAN COUNCIL OF RESEARCH MEDICINE 2024. ICRM Annual Report 2023-2024.
- INTEGRATED DISEASE SURVEILLANCE PROGRAMME. 2025. *About IDSP* [Online]. Available: <https://idsp.mohfw.gov.in/index4.php?lang=1&level=0&linkid=313&lid=1592> [Accessed August 16th, 2025].
- KANT, L. & KRISHNAN, S. K. 2010. Information and communication technology in disease surveillance, India: a case study. *BMC Public Health*, 10, S11.

- KUMAR, A., GOEL, M. K., JAIN, R. B. & KHANNA, P. 2014. Tracking the implementation to identify gaps in integrated disease surveillance program in a block of district jhajjar (haryana). *J Family Med Prim Care*, 3, 213-5.
- KUMAR, A. & PRASAD, A. 2021. Surveillance of Dengue Vector, *Aedes aegypti* (L.) Mosquitoes in Udaipur District of South Rajasthan (India). *Bulletin of Pure & Applied Sciences- Zoology*, 40a, 238-249.
- KUMAR, G., BAHARIA, R., SINGH, K., GUPTA, S. K., JOY, S., SHARMA, A. & RAHI, M. 2024. Addressing challenges in vector control: a review of current strategies and the imperative for novel tools in India's combat against vector-borne diseases. *BMJ Public Health*, 2, e000342.
- MOURYA, D. T., YADAV, P. D., ULLAS, P. T., BHARDWAJ, S. D., SAHAY, R. R., CHADHA, M. S., SHETE, A. M., JADHAV, S., GUPTA, N., GANGAKHEDKAR, R. R., KHASNOBIS, P. & SINGH, S. K. 2019. Emerging/re-emerging viral diseases & new viruses on the Indian horizon. *Indian J Med Res*, 149, 447-467.
- MUTHENENI, S. R., MORSE, A. P., CAMINADE, C. & UPADHYAYULA, S. M. 2017. Dengue burden in India: recent trends and importance of climatic parameters. *Emerg Microbes Infect*, 6, e70.
- NATIONAL CENTER FOR VECTOR BORNE DISEASES CONTROL 2023. National Guidelines for Clinical Management of Dengue Fever. New Delhi.
- NATIONAL CENTRE FOR VECTOR BORNE DISEASES CONTROL 2025. List of Sentinel Surveillance Hospitals (869) for Dengue and Chikungunya for the year 2025.
- OFFICE OF THE PRINCIPAL SCIENTIFIC ADVISER TO THE GOVERNMENT OF INDIA. 2025. *National One Health Mission* [Online]. Available: <https://www.psa.gov.in/oneHealthMission> [Accessed August 16th, 2025].
- PANAGARIYA, A. 2008. *India: the emerging giant*, New York, N.Y., Oxford University Press.
- PILOT, E., MURTHY, G. V. S. & NITTAS, V. 2020. Understanding India's urban dengue surveillance: A qualitative policy analysis of Hyderabad district. *Global Public Health*, 15, 1702-1717.

- RODRIK, D. & SUBRAMANIAN, A. 2004. From "Hindu Growth" to Productivity Surge: The Mystery of the Indian Growth Transition. *National Bureau of Economic Research*.
- SARKAR, S., GANGARE, V., SINGH, P. & DHIMAN, R. C. 2019. Shift in Potential Malaria Transmission Areas in India, Using the Fuzzy-Based Climate Suitability Malaria Transmission (FCSMT) Model under Changing Climatic Conditions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16, 3474.
- SCHENK, C. R. 2011. International economic relations since 1945. 1st ed. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.
- SHEPARD, D. S., HALASA, Y. A., TYAGI, B. K., ADHISH, S. V., NANDAN, D., KARTHIGA, K. S., CHELLASWAMY, V., GABA, M., ARORA, N. K. & THE INCLIN STUDY, G. 2014. Economic and disease burden of dengue illness in India. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*, 91, 1235-1242.
- SRINIVASAN, T. N. & TENDULKAR, S. D. 2003. *Reintegrating India with the World Economy*, Institute for International Economics.
- THAKUR, P. 2016. *Delhi under-reporting dengue toll, cases; CAG* [Online]. Times of India. Available:
<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/delhi/delhi-under-reporting-dengue-toll-cases-cag/articleshow/54515812.cms> [Accessed August 16th, 2025].
- TIMES OF INDIA. 2025a. *Chennai prepares for Peak Dengue Season; Adyar, Shollinganallur Lead in Cases* [Online]. Times of India. Available:
<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/chennai/chennai-prepares-for-peak-dengue-season-adyar-shollinganallur-lead-in-cases/articleshow/122801101.cms> [Accessed August 16th, 2025].
- TIMES OF INDIA. 2025b. *Mosquito larvae in accumulated water: 706 citizens get notices* [Online]. Available:
<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/nagpur/mosquito-larvae-in-accumulated-water-706-citizens-get-notices/articleshow/121008139.cms> [Accessed August 16th, 2025].
- YASOBANT, S., TADVI, R., BRUCHHAUSEN, W. & SAXENA, D. B. 2024. Application of the One Health Surveillance (OHS) Matrix to Evaluate the Disease Surveillance Systems in Gujarat, India: A Policy Content Analysis. *J Epidemiol Glob Health*, 14, 1633-1641.

YASOBANT, S., TADVI, R. & SAXENA, D. B. 2025. Preparedness for One Health Surveillance System: A qualitative in-depth exploration in Gujarat, India. *IJID One Health*, 6, 100055.